

How has resource abundance influenced income inequality in Central Asia? A case study of Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan

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Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my professor Dr. Nargiza Alimukhammedova for invaluable guidance, feedback and constant encouragement throughout the duration of this project

Moreover, I am very grateful to Dr. Lyusyena Kirakosyan who helped me to strengthen my knowledge regarding social analysis tools as well as data collection.

Abstract

As the world is becoming more and more globalized, income inequality seems to be a relevant issue to the world. In fact, it is speculated that the top 1% of the adult earners in the world will hold 45.8% of all wealth in the world in 2020. Central Asia is no stranger to this problem. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Central Asian countries, as well as many other former Soviet Union members, saw a huge spike in income inequality across the region. This research tests whether one of the key qualities of the Central Asian countries – resource abundance – has contributed to income inequality in the region.

The research has first identified how resource abundance (measured by resource rent-to-GDP-ratio) causes income inequality and what other factors could have caused income inequality in the region. Then, the data was gathered for each factor for available years and was run in a country-level linear regression model to see the relationship between resource abundance and income inequality. After that, it tested how consistent it is with past research to identify potential causality.

The research has concluded that for Kazakhstan, resource abundance seems to have little influence on income inequality, and the major cause is institutional quality. For Kyrgyz Republic, there's actually a negative relationship, indicating that higher resource abundance is associated with lower income inequality, mainly due to lower average resource abundance and higher social spending. For the rest of the countries, accurate conclusions couldn't have been drawn, mainly due to lack of proper data for the countries

Keywords: Gini index, resource rents, resource abundance, Rule of Law, World Bank, Central Asia, resource curse

Introduction

Even countries with high rates of economic development still face income inequality to some extent, making it inevitable. While many blame it on capitalism, this issue was present in the largest communist country – Soviet Union – as well, though the reported rates show Gini index as low as 0.289 (Falkingham, 1999). However, following the dissolution of this communist federation, the issue of income inequality was exacerbated by market reforms in the newly independent states. While this transition has surely contributed to raised income inequality levels, it cannot be fully attributed to this factor.

Central Asia consists of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz Republic, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan – all post-transition countries. In these countries, past research has looked at the role of educational inequalities (Milanovic 1996, 1999; Kattuman & Redmond, 2001); the emergence of the private sector, the growing share of an informal economy (Rosser, Rosser, & Ahmed 2000); insufficient government transfers; and the growing difference between urban and rural populations (Milanovic, 1996, 1999) when it comes to income inequality.

Other studies about income inequality in the region focused either on the effects (Rózsás, 2002) or trends (Anderson & Pomfret, 2004). Other papers were aimed at analyzing just living standards (Felipe & Kumar, 2010), economic performance (Yormirzoyev, 2021), or economic development (White, 2008) in the post-Soviet Central Asian countries.

However, none of these papers have focused on how resource abundance could have affected income inequality in Central Asia when past research has shown that resource abundant countries tend to show higher income inequality (Anyanwu, Anyanwu, & Cieřlik, 2021). While the scope of that paper has overlooked Central Asia countries, this paper aims to find the relationship between resource abundance and income inequality in the region.

Literature review

Understanding income inequality and resource abundance

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (n.d.) defines income inequality as “the difference in how income is distributed among the population.” Income inequality is measured by the Gini coefficient, which takes values ranging from 0 (complete equality) to 1 (complete inequality). This index is calculated from the Lorenz curve, which illustrates the cumulative share of total income held by the cumulative share of the population. Specifically, the Gini coefficient is calculated as the ratio of the area between equidistributional line and actual Lorenz curve to total area under equidistributional line, as illustrated in the graph below.

Figure 1

Source: Food and Agriculture Organization 2005

Historically, income inequality has been shown to increase in transitional economies. Milanovic (1998) compiled Gini indices for a sample of such economies pre- and post-transition to conclude that with the exception of Slovakia, where it slightly improved, the remaining economies experienced significant deterioration. For example, Kyrgyz Republic and Russia saw their Gini indices more than double.

In this paper, resource abundance is defined as the share of natural resource rents in a country's GDP. This includes income from oil, natural gas, coal, minerals, and forest products, measured by the World Bank. Resource-rich countries are those whose natural resources account for 20% of government revenue or 20% of export revenue (Cust, et. al., 2022).

According to Aguirre (2023), those countries whose natural-resource-rents-to-GDP ratio exceeds 10% are considered resource abundant. While Western countries are usually not resource abundant, African, Latin American and Middle Eastern countries are rich in resources. In Central Asia, the aforementioned ratio ranged from 9.05 in Tajikistan to 26.84 in Kazakhstan, which indicates that most Central Asian countries are resource abundant (see Table 1-5).

How abundance of resources affects income inequality

While one may expect that having high volumes of natural resources may actually benefit the economy, in some cases it may be the opposite, which is called "resource curse." The Natural Resource Governance Institute (NRGI) (2015) describes the resource curse as follows:

The resource curse (also known as the paradox of plenty) refers to the failure of many resource-rich countries to benefit fully from their natural resource wealth, and for governments in these countries to respond effectively to public welfare needs. While one might expect to see better development outcomes after countries discover natural resources, resource-rich countries tend to have higher rates of conflict and authoritarianism, and lower rates of economic stability and economic growth, compared to their non-resource-rich neighbors.

Parcerro and Papyrakis (2016) employ a cross-country panel design using the Standardized World Income Inequality Database (SWIID). To address the potential under-reporting of inequality in oil-rich countries, they apply a Heckman selection correction. Their results indicate that, after adjusting for reporting bias, oil abundance tends to be associated with lower income inequality — but the effect weakens or reverses in cases of extreme oil dependence.

Using synthetic control method over the period 1947-2009, Hartwell, Horvath, Horvathova & Popova (2022) find that there could be a negative causation between resource abundance and income inequality in developed countries. For example, uncovering new resources was associated with a significant drop in income inequality in Denmark and a more moderate decrease in Norway and the Netherlands. These findings posit a counter-argument against the "resource-curse-raises-inequality" view observed in various countries. But there should be consideration in the differences of countries and economic and developmental levels. In the case of such developed countries, inequality goes down, and not up, because of several factors, one of which is institutional quality. Compared to undeveloped countries, such economies had more mature democracies, strong property rights frameworks and broad

welfare states when oil and gas booms hit. This ensures that rents go towards public services instead of political elites. Another factor is the quantity of discovered resources, where there is a demonstrated ideal range that is large enough to finance redistribution, but small enough to prevent rent-seeking behaviour.

Other factors affecting income inequality

Besides income inequality, there are other factors that could have influenced income inequality in Central Asia. For example, Gupta et. al. (1998) suggests that corruption could lead to worsening of income inequality because of a flawed tax system and social spending with the wealthy being able to influence government decision making to make policies in favour of them rather than the poor. In fact, Mauro (1998) finds that higher corruption is found to be associated with lower education and health spending. Because of “uncertain rules of the game” in a corrupt economy, those who have good connections to authorities tend to “win” more returns for their investments while this return may be lower for the less-connected, thereby discouraging investment by the poor on human or physical capital or land and further accentuating the income inequality in the economy.

Sözen, Sarı, and Çelik (2011) argue that income inequality itself may exacerbate corruption in the Central Asian Republics. While this claim is theoretically plausible and consistent with some cross-country evidence (Gupta et al., 1998), the causal direction between inequality and corruption is very vague. In practice, corruption and inequality often reinforce each other, resulting in a feedback loop.

Another factor potentially increasing income inequality could be government spending as redistributive government policies may lower Gini coefficient in the area. Specifically, Doumbia (2019) finds that one percentage increase in total-spending-to-GDP ratio results in 0.8 to 1 percent less income inequality. Also the same study suggests that the impact on income inequality is lower, especially, when social spending is financed by cuts in defense and health spending. In the Central Asian context, the redistributive impact of public spending is uneven. Compared to Kazakhstan or Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan has consistently allocated a larger share of GDP to social expenditure (see Tables 1-5). Effectiveness of government spending on reducing income inequality also depends on its composition as well. In Kazakhstan, the social spending has mainly gone towards Astana, Expo 2017, and mega-infrastructure programs rather than distributive policies (Pomret, 2019). Similarly, Turkmenistan has spent hydrocarbon revenues on monumental architecture and showcase events in Ashgabat instead of redistributive policies.

Moreover, Blancheton (2021) finds that income inequality could be affected by institutional quality of the country too though this impact would depend on the country's stage of development. At early stages of development, rising public expenditure could lead to higher income inequality. However, this effect could be reversed once the institutional quality of the country increases. This is particularly important in Central Asia's case as they have less mature democratic institutions. As a result, government spending could have had less distributive effects as well.

Consequences of income inequality

Although income inequality is perceived as a social issue, it has several macroeconomic implications. For example, income inequality can lead to concentration of power among the elites which, in turn, could lead to sub-optimal use of resources, reductions in investments in public infrastructure, economic and political instability and crisis (Dabla-Norris E. A. et al., 2015). Moreover, the same study finds that rising income inequality could lead to rent-seeking behaviour, leading to resource misallocation, nepotism and corruption.

Besides those, income inequality caused by resource abundance may also impact economic growth. For example, Want et al. (2021) has found that in 85 countries, the drag of income inequality on economic growth becomes twice as large once countries become resource-abundant. The issues created within development also create new challenges and costs of living crises for the poor. Rosser Jr et. al. (2000) finds a strong correlation between informal economy and income inequality in Turkey as both of them have moved in the same direction over the time series analysis that has been carried out in the research. Findings go as far as to suggest that the unequal economy of Turkey causes a larger informal sector since it is the poor who demand cheaper products from the informal sector.

Even though increased income inequality's negative effects may seem straightforward, lower income inequality could have negative implications on the economy as well. Behzadan et al. (2017) examine Denmark's experience, where income inequality alternately widened and narrowed during a resource boom. When inequality rose, the demand surge for non-tradables was relatively muted, leading to limited exchange rate appreciation. Conversely, when inequality declined, stronger demand pressures pushed the exchange rate upward, which harmed the traded-growth sector. Since productivity growth in the long run is largely driven by learning-by-doing in the tradable sector, a sharper Dutch disease effect ultimately slows aggregate growth. Paradoxically, this implies that a resource windfall that reduces inequality may, in fact, worsen long-term growth prospects.

Methodology

Models and variables

The equation below models the relationship between income inequality and resource abundance:

$$\text{INEQUALITY}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{ResourceAbundance}_{it} + u_{it}$$

(Model 1)

However, considering that inequality is influenced by factors beyond resource abundance, this model could give misleading results, so the model is expanded to include other factors that also affect income inequality too:

$$\text{INEQUALITY}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{ResourceAbundance}_{it} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{GovtExpenditure}_{it} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Corruption} + \beta_4 \cdot \text{Institutional Quality}_{it} + u_{it}$$

(Model 2)

Here i is used to indicate country, t is used to denote for year and u is an error term for random unexplained factors.

In order to quantify the model, each factor is measured by a certain variable of its own. First of all, income inequality (INEQUALITY_{it}) is measured by the Gini coefficient. Next, resource abundance ($\text{ResourceAbundance}_{it}$) of countries for different years is measured by resource-rent-to-GDP ratio of countries. Similarly, the government-expenditure-to-GDP ratio is used to quantify the government expenditure ($\text{GovtExpenditure}_{it}$).

This particular simple cross-country linear model was used instead of panel estimators such as Fixed Effects (FE) and Random Effects (RE). This is because, first of all, the paper aims to analyze the relationship between resource abundance and income inequality separately for each country instead of pooling them together. Secondly, countries like Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan have a significant amount of missing values which wouldn't make using panel estimators possible

Corruption Perceptions index (CPI) is used to assess the level of corruption in countries. This is a measure developed by Transparency International which scores and ranks countries by their perceived levels of public sector corruption, as assessed by experts and business executives. It takes values between 0 and 100, with 0 meaning very corrupt and 100 indicating clean from corruption.

Measuring institutional quality isn't straightforward as no indicator cannot fully represent the true quality of government institutes. However, past research focused on measuring institutional quality, such as Bösch (2021) or Gallego-Álvarez (2021), has used Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI). These indicators correspond to around 200 countries and territories starting in 1996 and combine the views of a large number of enterprise, citizen, and expert survey respondents in industrialised and developing countries. They are based on over 30 individual data sources produced by a variety of surveys corresponding to think tanks, non-governmental organisations, international organisations, and private sector firms. The Worldwide Governance Indicators cover six broad dimensions of governance: voice and accountability, political stability and absence of violence, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, and control of corruption.

In this paper, only the Rule of Law estimates as part of WGI is used which captures perceptions of the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society, and in particular the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, the police, and the courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence. The Rule of Law was chosen among other dimensions of WGI because it most directly reflects enforcement of property rights, the quality of legal institutions, and constraints on elite capture — factors particularly relevant in resource-rich settings. Estimate gives the country's score on the aggregate indicator, in units of a standard normal distribution, i.e. ranging from approximately -2.5 to 2.5.

While results of Model 2 indicates that institutional quality plays a significant role in shaping income inequality in Kazakhstan (see Table 6), previous literature (e.g., Abdulahi et al., 2019; Sarmidi et al., 2012; Asongu, 2024) suggests that effect of resource abundance on development outcomes depends critically on the quality of institutions. Therefore, Model 3 was run on Kazakhstan to include interaction between institutional quality and resource abundance.

$$\text{INEQUALITY}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{ResourceAbundance}_t + \beta_2 \cdot \text{GovtExpenditure}_t + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Corruption}_t + \beta_4 \cdot \text{Institutional Quality}_t + \beta_5 \cdot (\text{ResourceAbundance}_t \times \text{Institutional Quality}_t) + u_t$$

(Model 3)

Similarly, Table 6 indicates a strong relationship between government expenditure and income inequality in the region, so Model 4 was run on Kyrgyz Republic to include interaction between government spending and resource abundance:

$$\text{INEQUALITY}_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot \text{ResourceAbundance}_t + \beta_2 \cdot \text{GovtExpenditure}_t + \beta_3 \cdot \text{Corruption}_t + \beta_4 \cdot \text{Institutional Quality}_t + \beta_5 \cdot (\text{ResourceAbundance}_t \times \text{GovtExpenditure}_t) + u_t$$

(Model 4)

Data

For most of the time, data collection for the following countries was no easy task as some of these countries didn't make data regarding their economy publicly available. The ones that

published it to the public don't have Gini coefficients for years before 2000. Also, resource-rent-to-GDP ratio and Government final consumption expenditure (% of GDP) numbers are available only up to 2021. Therefore, the information used in this paper will only include metrics from 2000 to 2021.

Moreover, it's worth mentioning that Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan did not have information about their Gini indices for the following period. For Tajikistan, Gini indices were available for 1999, 2003, 2004, 2007, 2009, and 2015. For Uzbekistan, the number of years were even lower, including only 1998, 2000, 2002, 2003 and 2022. Turkmenistan, on the other hand, has reported this metric only once in 1998. So the model above is run for only Kazakhstan and Kyrgyz Republic.

Table 1 and Table 2 show the sample data used to run the regressions above.

Table 1: Trends in Gini coefficient, resource rent to GDP ratio, government expenditure, corruption index and Rule of Law Metrics in Kazakhstan (2000-2021)

Year	GINI	Resource rent to GDP ratio	Government final consumption expenditure (% of GDP)	Corruption Index	Rule of law
2021	29.2	26.842317332729	11.27	37	-0.508970081806183
2020	28.7	12.840695196489	12.74	38	-0.467089861631393
2019	28	17.925973852542	9.13	34	-0.510017037391663
2018	27.8	20.782964692625	8.32	31	-0.503466427326202
2017	27.5	14.897596398127	10.54	31	-0.48727560043335
2016	27.2	11.033682057513	11.63	29	-0.513149499893188
2015	26.8	9.3287650054609	11.63	28	-0.515273213386536
2014	27	17.250080261125	10.69	29	-0.609486997127533
2013	27.1	18.21874881505	10.17	26	-0.716409802436829
2012	28.2	21.982696768059	11.52	28	-0.772899031639099
2011	28	25.768820541937	10.48	27	-0.641633808612823
2010	28	21.74414415796	10.81	29	-0.695639729499817
2009	28.2	21.585858472187	11.66	27	-0.723441064357758
2008	28.5	33.248025247633	10.19	22	-0.926385998725891
2007	30.1	26.491531190732	11.05	21	-1.03190290927887
2006	30.2	28.790456312151	10.18	26	-1.10211932659149
2005	39.8	30.28175844704	11.25	26	-0.953236162662506
2004	31.8	28.254058031754	11.61	22	-1.12646734714508
2003	33.7	22.877766216541	11.26	24	-1.09689700603485
2002	34.8	23.085280684426	11.61	23	-1.20242607593536
2001	36	20.961687101826	13.41	27	-1.2

2000	36.6	27.319067298716	12.08	30	-1.15091466903687
Mean	30.15	21.887	11.06	27.95	-0.7934
Median	28.35	21.863	11.26	27.50	-0.7199

Table 2: Trends in Gini coefficient, resource rent to GDP ratio, government expenditure, corruption index and Rule of Law Metrics in Kyrgyz Republic (2000-2021)

Year	GINI	Resource rent to GDP ratio	Government final consumption expenditure(% of gdp)	Corruption Index	Rule of Law
2021	28.8	11.51	16.6	27	-1.09876596927643
2020	29.0	6.53	18.4	31	-0.962204277515411
2019	29.7	7.24	15.7	30	-0.914637327194214
2018	27.7	4.67	17.2	29	-0.928701460361481
2017	27.3	8.76	17.1	29	-0.947072088718414
2016	26.8	5.61	17.4	28	-1.04514920711517
2015	29.0	4.25	17.8	28	-1.01451683044434
2014	26.8	4.07	17.5	27	-0.936236679553986
2013	28.8	5.72	18.4	24	-1.11533272266388
2012	27.4	3.58	20.1	24	-1.1348477602005
2011	27.8	10.20	18.2	21	-1.19611263275146
2010	30.1	9.81	18.1	20	-1.26945745944977
2009	29.9	4.46	18.4	19	-1.32975375652313
2008	31.5	4.30	17.5	18	-1.38291394710541
2007	33.9	1.07	17.1	21	-1.32194709777832
2006	37.4	1.83	18.0	22	-1.31729280948639
2005	32.6	3.10	17.5	23	-1.1232408285141
2004	34.8	3.42	18.2	22	-0.793166995048523
2003	28.7	3.40	16.8	21	-0.760160028934479
2002	30.3	3.31	18.6	24.16	-0.853914260864258
2001	30.2	3.53	17.5	24.09	-0.9
2000	31.0	4.15	20.0	23.70	-0.906720697879791
Mean	29.98	5.205	17.82	24.36	-1.0569
Median	29.35	4.275	17.65	24.00	-1.0298

Gini indices for both countries were taken from World Bank official measures. However, the World Bank didn't release the Gini index for Kazakhstan for 2000, so the index for this year is taken from an Astana Times article by Anna Alshanskaya (2025).

Resource rent to GDP ratio and Government final consumption expenditure (% of GDP), similarly, were taken from the World Bank too. CPI measures are all taken from Transparency International. However, CPI for Kyrgyzstan for 2000-2002 wasn't available so the OLS regression model was used to predict the index for the following years (Figure 2). Rule of Law Estimate for 2001 weren't available so approximations were used for that year.

Figure 2

For Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan, Gini coefficients weren't available for every year from 2000 to 2021. Therefore, in order to assess income inequality in these countries, the P10/P50 ratio was used, which is the ratio of share of total income held by top 10% earners of the country (P10) to the share of total income held by bottom 50% of the country (P50). The data is taken from the World Inequality Database (WID) to measure this ratio. While these measures offer broader coverage, Gini and P10/P50 ratio aren't entirely comparable across countries.

Table 3: Trends in P10/P50 ratio, resource rent to GDP ratio, government expenditure, corruption index and Rule of Law Metrics in Uzbekistan (2000-2021)

Year	P10/P50	Resource rent to GDP ratio	Government expenditure(% of gdp)	Corruption Index	Rule of Law
2021	2.8417721519	20.5	14.9	28	-0.921241641044617
2020	2.8417721519	9.1	14.6	26	-1.11787843704224
2019	2.8417721519	10.9	14.5	25	-1.08285343647003
2018	2.8417721519	18.7	12.1	23	-1.09895992279053
2017	2.8417721519	12.0	11.3	22	-1.13459193706512
2016	2.7469135802	6.7	14.1	21	-1.12917804718018
2015	2.8176100629	7.3	13.6	19	-1.13871383666992
2014	2.8176100629	10.4	13.2	18	-1.1344530582428
2013	2.8176100629	14.7	13.3	17	-1.23550093173981
2012	2.8176100629	17.3	12.4	17	-1.29927587509155
2011	2.8176100629	19.1	12.0	16	-1.45240187644958
2010	2.81761006289308	14.8	12.5	16	-1.41664183139801
2009	2.8176100629	18.6	15.5	17	-1.32619547843933
2008	2.8176100629	30.1	15.9	18	-1.17363584041595
2007	2.8176100629	22.6	15.6	17	-1.22470498085022
2006	2.8176100629	25.5	15.3	21	-1.45359468460083
2005	2.8176100629	15.4	15.9	22	-1.47870898246765
2004	2.8176100629	18.8	16.2	23	-1.33680975437164
2003	2.8176100629	21.8	17.4	24	-1.24661719799042
2002	2.6094674556	20.3	18	29	-1.44006717205048
2001	2.7300613497	23.6	18.5	27	-1.3
2000	2.8598726115	13.0	18.7	24	-1.200798869133
Mean	2.818	16.87	14.80	21.36	-1.2429
Median	2.808	17.95	14.75	21.50	-1.2301

Table 4: Trends in P10/P50 ratio, resource rent to GDP ratio, government expenditure, corruption index and Rule of Law Metrics in Tajikistan (2003-2021)

Year	P10/P50	Resource rent to GDP ratio	Government expenditure	Corruption Index	Rule of Law
2021	2.45562130177515	9	10.9	25	-1.20684373378754
2020	2.45562130177515	5.1	11.6	25	-1.25058948993683
2019	2.45562130177515	5.2	11.2	25	-1.2538548707962
2018	2.45562130177515	5.4	11.2	25	-1.30350601673126
2017	2.43529411764706	4.5	11.4	21	-1.37405633926392
2016	2.3757225433526	3.8	11.8	25	-1.16668653488159
2015	2.18579234972678	2.3	11.6	26	-1.07517385482788
2014	2.23333333333333	2.2	14	23	-1.0121363401413
2013	2.28813559322034	1.3	13.3	22	-1.26350378990173
2012	2.26404494382022	1.7	12.8	22	-1.2076199054718
2011	2.22222222222222	2	13.7	23	-1.23239934444427
2010	2.24022346368715	1.7	11.3	21	-1.21289575099945
2009	2.22905027932961	0.7	12.5	20	-1.27246570587158
2008	2.22651933701657	0.8	9.3	20	-1.29554963111877
2007	2.22950819672131	0.8	8.9	21	-1.29604709148407
2006	2.32022471910112	0.8	11.1	22	-1.18217408657074
2005	2.39080459770115	0.6	14.6	21	-1.10024237632751
2004	2.36571428571429	0.7	11.8	20	-1.18313717842102
2003	2.3757225433526	0.8	8.3	18	-1.06657803058624
Mean	2.327	2.60	11.65	22.37	-1.208
Median	2.320	1.70	11.60	22.00	-1.213

Table 5: Trends in P10/P50 ratio, resource rent to GDP ratio, government expenditure, corruption index and Rule of Law Metrics in Uzbekistan (2004-2019)

Year	P10/P50	Resource rent to GDP ratio	Government expenditure	Corruption Index	Rule of law
2019	3.72307692307692	13.5	12.3	19	-1.45872151851654
2018	3.72307692307692	20.1	12	20	-1.40002739429474
2017	3.68702290076336	13	15.2	19	-1.40987253189087
2016	3.62406015037594	9.7	9	22	-1.46458470821381
2015	3.42446043165468	15.5	9.6	18	-1.48155915737152
2014	3.48905109489051	20.2	6.6	17	-1.48835563659668
2013	3.58955223880597	27.5	6.1	17	-1.41998243331909
2012	3.61654135338346	30.9	5.9	17	-1.34476661682129
2011	3.61654135338346	34.3	6.6	16	-1.36186134815216

2010	3.65151515151515	23.2	7.1	16	-1.3807088136673
2009	3.68702290076336	22.9	7.4	18	-1.43329453468323
2008	3.58208955223881	57	7	18	-1.47331619262695
2007	3.45652173913043	49.3	9.8	20	-1.45370447635651
2006	3.51470588235294	51.5	11.7	22	-1.45997738838196
2005	3.48905109489051	43.2	14.6	18	-1.56595134735107
2004	3.33802816901408	44.1	13.9	20	-1.64104187488556
Mean	3.576	29.74	9.675	18.00	-1.456
Median	3.603	25.35	9.300	18.56	-1.452

However, it's worth mentioning that the source used to obtain P10 and P50 measures for Uzbekistan aren't reliable as the data is ranked on star on WID, which means that the numbers are "based on low-quality surveys for which no tax data is available. Imputed corrections are applied to compensate for the lack of tax data." This is also evident from the fact that the P10/P50 ratio was the same for most of the years.

Empirical analysis

Results of Model 2

Table 6: Correlation coefficient of Gini Coefficient in different countries in relation to other factors (*** p < 0.001; ** p < 0.01; * p < 0.05)

	Kazakhstan	Kyrgyz Republic	Tajikistan	Turkmenistan	Uzbekistan
Resource-rent-to-GDP-ratio	0.07	-0.45 *	0.04**	-0.00	0.00
Standard error	(0.12)	(0.20)	(0.01)	(0.00)	(0.00)
p-value	0.574	0.035	0.004	0.204	0.860
Govt. expenditure (% of GDP)	0.43	-0.42	0.00	0.01	-0.00
Standard error	(0.59)	(0.53)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.01)
p-value	0.481	0.437	0.818	0.315	0.719

Corruption Index	0.35	-0.23	-0.02	0.00	-0.01
Standard error	(0.18)	(0.17)	(0.01)	(0.01)	(0.00)
p-value	0.057	0.206	0.155	0.869	0.139
Rule of Law	-12.62 **	-2.36	0.03	1.19**	0.17
Standard error	(4.06)	(3.29)	(0.21)	(0.35)	(0.08)
p-value	0.005	0.483	0.886	0.006	0.053
N	22	22	19	16	22
R ² /R ² adjusted	0.687/0.613	0.414/0.272	0.532/0.398	0.645/0.516	0.345/0.190

Interestingly, this graph shows that in Kazakhstan, resource abundance and income inequality shows little to no correlation with little statistical significance with each other despite Kazakhstan having very high values of resource rent to GDP ratio. This is potentially due to Kazakhstan having higher mean and median Rule of Law scores compared to other counties in the region.

Instead, the Rule of Law seems to have a strong correlation with income inequality in the country, indicating that for Kazakhstan, institutional qualities play a far larger role to distribute income compared to resource abundance. This is consistent with previous research carried out by Blancheton (2021) which indicates that income inequality could be heavily influenced by institutional qualities of the country.

However, for Kyrgyz Republic, there is a statistically significant negative relationship between resource abundance and income inequality, suggesting that increasing resource abundance could be lowering income inequality in the region. Although this could come off as surprising considering Kyrgyz Republic had lower institutional qualities compared to Kazakhstan, which is reflected by mean and median scores for both Corruption Indices and Rule of Law Estimates, the fact that Kyrgyz Republic is less resource abundant compared to Kazakhstan should be taken into account. That could mean that because Kyrgyz Republic isn't as resource heavy as Kazakhstan is, rents from resources actually decreased income inequality in the country. This could potentially mean that Kyrgyz Republic hasn't reached a point where resource rents are big enough to be able to worsen influence income inequality which is a case similar to aforementioned Parcerro and Papyrakis (2016) and Hartwell et. al. (2022) findings.

Another possible explanation could be the case where Kyrgyz Republic is more successful than Kazakhstan in distributing earnings through proper social spending, which is reflected

by higher mean and median for government spending in Kyrgyz Republic compared to Kazakhstan.

For other countries, proper conclusions cannot be drawn due to low quality of data. For Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan, relationship seems to be 0 which is due to the fact that P10 and P50 measures had remained fairly the same for each country throughout the years, mainly because of poor data collection. Even though Tajikistan seems to have a statistically significant relationship between resource abundance and income inequality, this could potentially be misleading due to low quality of data.

Results of Model 3 and Model 4

Table 7: Results of Model 3 and Model 4

	Kyrgyzstan	Kazakhstan
Resource-rent-to-GDP-ratio	3.9101	-0.03502
Standard error	(4.3034)	(0.32974)
p-value	0.377	0.917
Govt. expenditure (% of GDP)	0.8026	0.42309
Standard error	(1.3181)	(0.60701)
p-value	0.551	0.496
Corruption Index	-0.2754	0.35469
Standard error	(0.1781)	(0.17598)
p-value	0.142	0.061
Rule of Law	-2.4355	-0.03502
Standard error	(3.2883)	(0.32974)
p-value	0.470	0.404

Resource Abundance × Government expenditure	-0.2488	-
Standard error	(0.2453)	-
p-value	0.325	-
Resource Abundance × Rule of Law	-	-0.14918
Standard error	-	(0.44707)
p-value	-	0.743
N	22	22
R ² /R ² adjusted	0.4491/0.277	0.689 / 0.592

For Kyrgyzstan, the interaction term between government expenditure and resource abundance was introduced to see if fiscal spending moderates the relationship between resource abundance and income inequality. However, results for the country seem to be statistically insignificant. This is because Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis showed a severe multicollinearity between resource abundance and government spending, with VIF values exceeding 500. This suggests a near-linear relationship between these variables, which substantially inflates standard errors and renders coefficient estimates unreliable.

The extremely high VIFs are consistent with the economic structure of the Kyrgyz Republic, where changes in resource revenues and government expenditure are closely linked through fiscal dependence on commodity rents. Consequently, the model cannot empirically separate their independent effects, even though the theoretical expectation of redistribution through public spending remains valid.

Similarly, when the interaction term was introduced for Kazakhstan, the model's explanatory power declined and none of the coefficients remained statistically significant. Similar to Kyrgyzstan, VIF tests confirmed severe multicollinearity, with VIF values of 16.5 for resource rents, 32.5 for the Rule of Law, and 70.8 for their interaction. This suggests that explanatory variables are highly correlated, obscuring coefficient significance. From this outcome, it can be inferred that resource abundance and institutional qualities move together in Kazakhstan and that the moderating effect of institutions on inequality cannot be empirically verified with the available data.

Conclusions

The main contribution of this study is to provide a comparative case study of two of the most data-accessible and institutionally divergent resource-rich states – Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan – in Central Asia.

In Kazakhstan, institutional quality shows a stronger correlation with income inequality than resource abundance, but interaction term between resource rent and institutional quality was statistically insignificant and had high multicollinearity. This suggests that while institutional quality and resource abundance are closely linked, their combined effect on inequality cannot be empirically verified with the available data. Therefore, institutional quality influences income inequality directly rather than moderating how resource abundance influences income inequality

In Kyrgyzstan, on the other hand, interaction terms between government expenditure and resource abundance carried the expected negative sign, but lacked statistical significance. with VIFs above 500 indicating that government spending and resource revenues move almost in tandem. This reflects the fiscal dependence of the budget on resource revenue, limiting the model's ability to isolate the redistributive channel statistically. Nevertheless, the observed patterns remain consistent with theoretical expectations of a more redistributive fiscal framework.

Limitations

One of the major limitations of the research was availability of data. For Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan, P10/P50 ratios from World Inequality Database (WID) were used instead of Gini indices as latter metrics weren't available for these countries. However, the quality of data on the website was ranked one star for all countries, indicating that it was "based on low-quality surveys for which no tax data is available. Imputed corrections are applied to compensate for the lack of tax data." Therefore, it was difficult to make any proper conclusions about those countries.

Also, The need to use non-comparable distributional metrics (Gini vs. P10/P50) for Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Tajikistan prevented robust cross-country comparison, forcing the analysis to prioritize the findings for Kazakhstan and the Kyrgyz Republic where high-quality Gini data was available.

Moreover, the scope of the research considers about 20 years because that was the amount of years for which data was available. This could mean that the results are susceptible to shocks or outliers, like oil-price collapses.

Further research should focus on obtaining more quality values for used metrics to improve the outcomes of the results. Collecting higher-quality and longer time-series data would

improve the robustness of the interaction models and help clarify the moderating roles of institutions and fiscal policy. For Kazakhstan, subnational analyses could investigate whether regional disparities in resource wealth contribute to inequality between resource-rich and non-resource regions. For the Kyrgyz Republic, detailed qualitative or mixed-methods studies of social spending could help determine whether the observed negative relationship between government expenditure and inequality reflects intentional redistribution or fiscal dependence on resource rents.

Policy recommendations

The findings suggest that improving institutional quality and fiscal transparency alone will not resolve inequality linked to resource dependence in Central Asia unless deeper structural reforms accompany them. In Kazakhstan, where centralized management of resource rents enables elite capture, reforms should target the *structure of revenue distribution* rather than merely the rules governing it. Decentralizing a portion of oil and mineral revenues to local governments, conditional on independent audits, could limit the concentration of fiscal power and enhance accountability. International initiatives such as the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI) and World Bank governance programs can play a pivotal role by requiring member governments to disclose disaggregated revenue and expenditure data.

In the Kyrgyz Republic, where government expenditure is closely tied to resource rents, structural reforms should focus on diversifying fiscal sources and strengthening expenditure monitoring to ensure that social spending serves redistributive objectives rather than reinforcing fiscal dependence. Partnerships with international development agencies could facilitate capacity-building and technical assistance to design social spending frameworks insulated from commodity price volatility.

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